

FABRICATION OF HIERARCHICAL POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES WITH CAPILLARY-DENSIFIED ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBE REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

To design next-generation hierarchical polymer nanocomposites (PNCs), scalable processing techniques such as vertically aligned carbon nanotube (A-CNT) growth, solvent-mediated CNT capillary densification, and capillary-assisted polymer infusion are attractive methods to create high-density and morphology-controlled bulk nanostructured materials. In this work, multiwalled A-CNT aerospace-grade infusion epoxy PNCs with mm-tall capillary-densified CNT cell and pin patterned reinforcement are fabricated for the first time, and their process-structure relationships are analyzed as a function of A-CNT volume fraction (V_f) and pattern type via scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Raman spectroscopy, and X-ray diffraction (XRD). These analyses provide multi-scale information to show how CNT confinement in dense cell and pin patterns (~8% CNT V_f in the cell and pin walls) influences polymer infiltration, wetting, and the CNT-matrix morphology. SEM and XRD results reveal that CNT alignment is consistently maintained in the epoxy matrix during processing, and SEM images show how the cell and pin PNCs exhibit CNT-matrix pull-out during fracture. Raman analysis shows that the atomic-scale defect density decreases with increasing CNT V_f in the PNCs, which is due to the greater CNT contribution to the spectra compared to the amorphous epoxy matrix. XRD further quantifies how the A-CNT walls dominate the diffraction patterns at higher CNT V_f in the cell and pin PNCs. Through these analyses, this study provides new insights into both the synthesis and multi-scale structure of hierarchical CNT PNCs, supporting the development and integration of advanced nano-engineered composites using facile patterning and densification techniques.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their advantaged multifunctional properties, high volume fraction (V_f) aligned carbon nanotubes (A-CNTs) are top candidates to enhance the strength, toughness, and thermal conductivity of polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) [1-3] and provide dense interfacial reinforcement in aerospace composite laminates, a process termed ‘nanostitching’ [4]. While it has been challenging to create high-density, shape-tunable, and large-area CNT structures to improve the versatility of PNCs, recent work has enabled the simple and predictable capillary densification [5-8] of mm-scale tall CNT arrays with high substrate adhesion [9,10]. This allows CNT PNC process-structure-property relations to be studied systematically at a variety of CNT V_f , length scales, and pattern sizes (see Figure 1), with CNTs spanning several orders of magnitude in height, density, and hierarchy [3-9].

These new processing capabilities enable the fabrication of PNCs reinforced with dense, patterned A-CNT architectures that can be designed with a variety of morphologies, such as cell networks and pins as shown in Figure 1, which are created by densifying bulk-scale or patterned A-CNT arrays, respectively [6,7]. Solid pins and long-range cell networks can be formed by densifying A-CNT arrays within small and large pattern sizes (s) [5-9], respectively, with the critical pattern size (s_{cr}) separating each morphology for a given CNT height (h) (see Figure 1). Different patterns and CNT V_f in the densified cell and pin walls are therefore achievable by tuning the processing conditions and system parameters, such as post-growth annealing for increased CNT-substrate adhesion, variable solvent surface tension, substrate pre-patterning to tune s , and CNT growth time to vary h . Tuning these

parameters creates nano- to mm-scale densified structures with CNT V_f up to 30–40% that can be predicted based on elastocapillary densification theory [6,7].

Figure 1: Illustrations showing an overview of the capillary densification of A-CNT arrays into (a-b) dense cell and pin architectures with tunable height (h), wall thickness (t), pattern size (s), cell width (w), and CNT volume fraction ($V_f \approx w/t_c$ for cells and $V_f \approx s/t_p$ for pins). Pins are formed from A-CNTs densified in a pattern size smaller than the critical pattern size (*i.e.*, $s < s_{cr}$). (c) Illustration of dense CNTs as hierarchical polymer nanocomposite (PNC) reinforcement and laminate reinforcement.

However, to investigate the potential use of these newly-developed CNT architectures for next-generation high-strength composite reinforcement in aerospace-grade polymer matrices, it is necessary to determine how polymer matrix infusion at high A-CNT V_f (*i.e.*, greater V_f than the as-grown array value of 1% A-CNTs [6,7]) influences the structure, morphology, and mechanical behavior of PNCs for a given h value [3,11,12]. Past work on bulk A-CNT PNCs highlights the benefits of using vertically aligned CNTs for advanced composite fabrication up to CNT V_f of $\sim 20\%$ in an epoxy matrix [2,11], as the alignment facilitates polymer infusion, wetting, and the controlled manufacturing of PNC test structures [12,13]. While early results are promising, these studies also underscore the need for greater understanding and tunability over the influential processing factors in PNC fabrication, which ultimately govern mechanical performance: CNT height, crystallinity/quality, alignment, and dispersion in the polymer matrix, and CNT-polymer interactions [3,13]. These factors will become even more critical when the CNT V_f increases, as CNT-polymer interactions and the resulting confinement and interfacial effects will dominate the synthesis, structure, and properties of these composite materials.

To address these outstanding challenges and support the development of experimentally-validated models to predict dense PNC behavior across length scales [2,3], this work presents an experimental process-structure study of capillary-densified CNT PNCs using an aerospace-grade polymer matrix (here RTM6 epoxy). The capillary densification of new mm-tall CNT cell and pin architectures followed by polymer infiltration and curing offers a means to study both CNT-polymer interactions at higher CNT V_f and enables the facile manufacturing of patterned structures for applications requiring specific shapes, such as sensor networks, structural health monitoring, and location-specific composite reinforcement, including ‘nanostitching’ between carbon fiber plies in composite laminates [4] (see Figure 1). Combined with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies of CNT wetting, alignment, and PNC fracture behavior, and additional structural quantification via Raman spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction (XRD), this work provides new insights into both the fabrication and multi-scale structure of hierarchical CNT composites to support the development and commercial integration of nano-engineered hybrid materials.

2 METHODS

2.1 CNT Array Synthesis, Thermal Cementation, and Capillary Densification

In this work, multiwalled CNT (MWCNT)-polymer (RTM6 epoxy) PNCs with mm-tall dense A-CNT cell and pin reinforcement were fabricated via the following steps, as shown in Figure 1. First, 1% V_f A-CNT arrays were synthesized via chemical vapor deposition (CVD), where the arrays were grown via a base-growth mechanism in a 22 mm internal diameter quartz tube furnace at atmospheric pressure and 700°C via a thermal catalytic CVD process, which uses ethylene as the carbon source and 600 ppm of water vapor added to the inert helium gas [14]. The CNTs were grown on a catalytic layer composed of 1 nm Fe on 10 nm Al_2O_3 deposited via electron beam physical vapor deposition [14] on 1 cm \times 1 cm SiO_2/Si substrates. To create patterned CNT arrays as densified CNT pin precursors, a subset of these substrates were mechanically scribed by hand to remove the Fe/ Al_2O_3 layers in rectangular grid patterns of one-dimensional pattern size $s \approx 500 \mu m$ on average. Due to the selective removal of catalyst inside the $\sim 40 \mu m$ -wide scribed grid lines, CNT arrays grew only in the rectangular pattern where the catalyst remained. As will be described herein, solid CNT pins formed from the capillary densification of these patterned A-CNTs since the scribed grids were smaller than the critical pattern size (s_{cr}) defining pin vs. cell formation (see Figure 1) [7,9]. A subset of SiO_2/Si substrates were left unpatterned (*i.e.*, $s = 1 \text{ cm} \gg s_{cr}$) as precursors for bulk-scale CNT cell networks that formed from the capillary densification of bulk-scale (non-patterned) A-CNT arrays [6].

Following substrate preparation, A-CNT arrays were grown to mm-scale height (h) via the CVD process described above. During the ~ 10 min CVD growth period, the growing CNTs self-assembled into aligned arrays with $h \approx 1$ mm (as measured via optical microscopy using a Carl Zeiss Axiotech 30 HD optical microscope) and were comprised of MWCNTs with an average outer diameter of ~ 8 nm (3–7 walls with ~ 5 nm inner diameter and intrinsic CNT density of $\approx 1.6 \text{ g/cm}^3$) [15], inter-CNT spacing of ~ 60 – 80 nm [16], and V_f of $\sim 1\%$ CNTs [15]. To increase the CNT-substrate adhesion strength of the as-grown CNTs, a thermal cementation (annealing) step was performed directly after the CNT growth period during the CVD process. The CNT arrays were subjected to 200 sccm of inert helium gas for 40 min [6,10] at 800°C, which resulted in a $\sim 10\times$ increase in the CNT-substrate adhesion force, ensuring that the mm-tall A-CNTs would not delaminate from the substrate during capillary densification [6,9].

After growth and cementation processing and before capillary densification, all A-CNT array samples were then exposed to a previously developed recipe for O_2 plasma treatment to remove the entangled CNT layer that often forms on top of the CNT array during the growth process [17], which can cause non-uniform densification under capillary forces [7]. Then, the CNTs were densified via a previously reported paper-soaking capillary densification technique using acetone as the solvent, as shown in Figure 1 [18], as this gentle process leads to slower wetting and therefore less CNT array delamination and disruption than direct immersion techniques [17]. Here, the paper acts as a hydrodynamic damper to allow the solvent to move into the CNT forest slowly, delicately wetting the

entire array from top to bottom [18]. The wetted CNT arrays were then left to dry under ambient pressure and temperature until all of the solvent had evaporated, during which time the bulk-scale and patterned cemented CNT arrays densified into mm-tall cellular networks and solid pins, respectively.

2.2 Polymer Nanocomposite Fabrication

Once A-CNT arrays were grown, cemented, and a subset were densified to create CNT cell and pin networks, the following steps were performed to create CNT/epoxy samples, which included CNT cell and pin PNCs (see Figures 1–3), bulk PNCs fabricated from as-grown 1% V_f A-CNT arrays, and cured neat RTM6 epoxy samples as a baseline. Fabrication of bulk CNT-epoxy PNCs via vacuum-assisted wetting and curing was performed by first placing free-standing 1% V_f A-CNT arrays (which were delaminated from their Si wafer growth substrate with a standard razor blade) into hollow cylindrical Al molds, ensuring that the primary CNT axis was orthogonal to the plane of the mold, following Ref. [14]. The A-CNT arrays were then infused with degassed RTM6 epoxy resin (Hexcel Corp., USA [19]) at 120°C for 1 hour and then cured at 180°C for 2 hours, following the manufacturer’s recommended cure cycle. RTM6 resin without the addition of CNTs was also cured in the same manner to create cured neat polymer samples.

Figure 2: Representative SEM images of a CNT-polymer nanocomposite (PNC) with dense CNT cell reinforcement in an epoxy matrix. (a) Top view of a bulk cemented A-CNT array formed into cells via capillary densification. (b) Side views of a cell PNC showing epoxy-wetted CNTs maintaining their alignment. (c) PNC fracture surface as prepared via room temperature hand fracture post-curing showing CNT bridging and pull-out from the epoxy matrix.

Figure 3: Representative SEM images of a CNT-polymer nanocomposite (PNC) with dense CNT pin reinforcement in an epoxy matrix. (a) Patterned cemented A-CNT arrays densified into vertical pins. Top views of (b) a large-area CNT pin PNC with epoxy-wetted CNT pins and (c) side view of the PNC fracture surface in the middle of a CNT pin, as prepared via room temperature hand fracture.

For the fabrication of CNT cell and pin PNCs, a ~2 mm-thick pool of warm degassed RTM6 resin was placed in an Al mold, and the cell and pin arrays (still attached to their Si wafer growth substrate) were attached to a vertical z-stage using SEM tape following Ref. [2]. The CNTs were then lowered into the pool of uncured epoxy for the capillary-assisted wetting/infiltration of polymer into the A-CNTs. After this, the fully wetted CNTs were removed from the pool, and the PNCs were cured following the steps above. Once cured, the Si wafer was pulled off vertically to delaminate the CNTs from the substrate for subsequent SEM and structural characterization, and a subset of the cell and pin PNCs were hand-fractured at room temperature to prepare PNC fracture surfaces for SEM imaging.

2.3 Morphological Characterization: SEM

High resolution SEM was used to image and characterize the overall morphology, pin pattern sizes (s), and geometry (cell width w , cell/pin wall thickness t , and V_f) of the capillary-densified CNT cell and pin architectures, as well as the morphology and fracture surfaces of the PNCs created via mechanical hand-fracture of the samples. This characterization was performed using a Zeiss Merlin scanning electron microscope with a 5 mm working distance and 5 kV accelerating voltage [6,7]. Figures 2a and 3a present SEM images showing the morphology of the cell and pins formed via the capillary densification of bulk-scale and patterned cemented A-CNT arrays, respectively (resulting in an average CNT V_f of ~8% and ~5% in the cell and pin walls, respectively, as determined via $V_f \approx w/t_c$ for cells and $V_f \approx s/t_p$ for pins [6,7]). Figures 2b-c and 3b-c show both top-view and side-view SEM images of the CNT cell and pin PNCs, respectively.

2.4 Structural Characterization: Raman Spectroscopy and XRD

2.4.1 Raman Spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was performed to quantify the atomic-scale structural evolution, chemical bonding character, and crystallinity of the A-CNT array, neat epoxy, and PNC samples in the high CNT V_f cell and pin regions, as this technique is broadly used to analyze defect densities and disorder in carbon-based materials [20-22]. Dominant spectral features include the Raman D-band, which is found at $\sim 1335\text{--}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and represents carbon defects and structural disorder in the (002) plane and breathing modes of sp^2 atoms in rings, and the Raman G-band, which is found at $\sim 1580\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and represents in-plane sp^2 bond stretching in rings and chains [20-22]. Epoxy Raman bands were also evaluated at $\sim 1190\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\sim 1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\sim 1614\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to C-C stretching and C=C aromatic chain vibrations in the cured polymer, respectively [23,24]. The intensity ratio of the D- and G-bands (I_D/I_G) and the relative band shapes (*e.g.*, breadth/size and location) were compared to determine the relative defect density and structural order in the samples [19-24], which allows for an investigation of the PNC structural evolution as a function of polymer infusion into higher V_f (capillary-densified) A-CNT arrays. Raman spectra were collected using a LabRam HR800 Raman microscope (Horiba Jobin Yvon) with 532 nm (2.33 eV) laser excitation through a 50 \times objective. Several spots on each sample (for at least 3 samples of each type) were studied to ensure that representative data were used when calculating I_D/I_G . The representative Raman spectra (smoothed using a 32-point moving average) for the as-grown A-CNT arrays, neat RTM6 epoxy, bulk 1% V_f PNCs, and CNT cell and pin PNCs are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Raman spectra (as labelled from bottom to top) of aligned MWCNTs (black), the high CNT V_f region within a cell PNC (blue) and pin PNC (red), a PNC with uniform 1% CNT V_f (purple), and neat RTM6 epoxy (green). The spectra show the structural evolution of PNCs as the A-CNT density (V_f) increases in the epoxy matrix via characterization of the carbon and epoxy Raman bands.

2.4.2. X-ray Diffraction

X-ray analysis was employed to examine the multi-scale structural evolution of CNT cell and pin PNCs as a function of CNT V_f using X-ray diffraction (XRD). In particular, this analysis was carried out to investigate the nanometer-scale feature sizes and orientations (including alignment), inter-layer spacing, structural strain, polymer interphase formation, nanoscale interaction effects, CNT wall-wall and carbon crystallite spacing, and polymer chain packing and crystallization effects due to increased CNT packing [2,11,14,25-33]. The (002), (100), and (110) carbon peaks were evaluated at positions of $2\theta \approx 25^\circ$, 43° , and 78° , respectively [14,31], and the broad epoxy peak was evaluated at $2\theta \approx 21^\circ$ [25,32,33]. A PANalytical X'Pert Pro XRD system in Bragg Brentano geometry was used to analyze the A-CNT array, neat epoxy, and PNC samples post-curing, where the CNTs were aligned/oriented normal to the stage so that the 2θ angle ranged from 0° (perpendicular to the CNT axis) to 90° (parallel to the CNT axis). Cu $K\alpha$ radiation was passed through a 2° anti-scattering slit with a 0.04 rad soller slit in X'celerator mode. The XRD experiments were performed at 45 kV and 40 mA with a scanning step interval of 0.02° (2θ). LaB₆ was used as the standard material for all measurements. The representative diffraction patterns (smoothed using a 32-point moving average) for the as-grown A-CNT arrays, neat RTM6 epoxy, bulk 1% V_f PNCs, and CNT cell and pin PNCs are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: X-ray diffraction (XRD) diffraction patterns (as labelled from bottom to top) of aligned MWCNTs (black), the high CNT V_f region within a cell PNC (blue) and pin PNC (red), a PNC with uniform 1% CNT V_f (purple), and neat RTM6 epoxy (green), with the vertical CNT alignment normal to the plane of the XRD stage. The diffraction patterns show the evolution of the (002), (100), and (110) carbon peaks at $2\theta \approx 25^\circ$, 43° , and 78° , respectively, and the broad epoxy peak at $2\theta \approx 21^\circ$ as the packing density of A-CNT reinforcement increases within the PNC's epoxy matrix.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 SEM Analysis

SEM imaging of the capillary-densified CNTs and CNT-epoxy PNCs (see Figures 2 and 3) provides multi-scale structural information to investigate the densified cell and pin morphologies, including the CNT array packing and alignment [6,7], and the morphology of the PNC surfaces, especially after fracture. Figures 2a and 3a show that the densified CNTs maintain their vertical alignment after capillary densification and exhibit an average CNT V_f of ~8% and ~5% in the cell and pin walls, respectively, as determined by $V_f [\%] \approx w/t_c$ for cells and $V_f [\%] \approx s/t_p$ for pins [6,7]. For the various PNCs, SEM illustrates how CNT confinement in the PNC epoxy matrix influences polymer infiltration, wetting, CNT dispersion/aggregation, and the CNT-matrix morphology, including the CNT alignment in the matrix and the composite microstructure after curing [1-3]. Figures 2b and 3b show that the polymer matrix completely fills the spaces between the CNT cells and pins and infuses into the densified CNT arrays, effectively wetting but not swelling the CNTs in the cell and pin walls while maintaining their alignment and dispersion within the matrix. This is consistent with the complete A-CNT wetting demonstrated for bulk-scale CNT-epoxy PNCs studied in previous work which had an A-CNT V_f up to ~20% [2,11], showing that the CNT cell and pin morphologies can serve as a viable architecture for composite reinforcement when facile tuning of the CNT V_f towards higher values is desired.

SEM imaging of the cell and pin PNCs is also used to analyze their cross-sectional fracture surfaces, which reflect the interfacial fracture behavior during the mechanical hand fracture of the PNCs after curing. As shown in Figures 2c and 3c, the PNC fracture behavior within the cell and pin sections is observed to be dominated by CNT bridging and pull-out/debonding from the matrix [1-3,23]. Here, the CNTs exhibit a pull-out caused by the interfacial debonding from the epoxy matrix owing to the resistance to the applied load [29], where failure is governed by the relative adhesion strength of the polymer and the A-CNTs, and the tensile stress exceeds the magnitude of the interaction forces between the polymer layer surrounding the CNTs and the CNTs themselves. This analysis gives a qualitative indication of the relative strength of CNT-matrix interactions and pull-out behavior based on CNT V_f in the cell and pin walls, which is consistent with the fracture morphologies of bulk CNT PNCs with thermoset polymer matrices and bulk CNT V_f up to ~20% [11,13,23].

3.2 Raman Spectroscopy Analysis

Raman spectroscopy is used to quantify the atomic-scale structural changes and bonding character evolution in the CNT-epoxy PNCs as a function of V_f for samples that were not fractured after curing. Raman spectra of the as-grown A-CNT array, neat RTM6 epoxy, bulk 1% V_f PNC, and CNT cell and pin PNCs presented in Figure 4 shows that the atomic-scale defect density decreases with increasing CNT V_f in the PNCs, and that the CNT structure is not significantly disrupted upon polymer infusion and curing. Here, the D- and G-bands of the high crystallinity CNTs are well defined at ~1350 cm^{-1} and ~1580 cm^{-1} for the cell and pin PNCs, representing sp^2 carbon defects and in-plane sp^2 carbon stretching [20-22]. As CNT V_f increases, these bands dominate the spectra compared to the amorphous epoxy bands at ~1190 cm^{-1} , ~1450 cm^{-1} , and ~1614 cm^{-1} , which correspond to C-C stretching and C=C aromatic chain vibrations in the RTM6 epoxy [23,24].

The I_D/I_G ratios and relative peak locations (frequencies) of the bands quantify the relative defect density and structural order in the samples, while also giving a qualitative indication of the strain on the CNTs in the dense cell and pin PNCs. The I_D/I_G ratio evolves from ~1.03 to 0.99 to 0.56 for the ~5% V_f pin PNC, ~8% V_f cell PNC, and A-CNT array, respectively, showing how higher V_f results in more structural order. Higher disorder is observed here for the 1% PNC since the polymer dominates the Raman spectrum. Additionally, an upshift in the D-band frequency is observed from ~1340 cm^{-1} to ~1346 cm^{-1} for the A-CNT array and cell PNC samples, respectively, showing that when an increased concentration of CNTs is added to the epoxy matrix, the epoxy intercalates with the CNT bundles and opens them during polymer infiltration and curing, producing a compressive strain in the composite

[34,35]. This is consistent with prior work showing Raman band upshifts for ~5wt% CNT-epoxy PNCs compared to pure CNTs [35] and a G-band downshift to lower frequencies when a tensile axial strain was applied to suspended CNTs [34]. These results show the efficacy of the epoxy to infuse between the CNT bundles during processing, as corroborated by the aforementioned SEM imaging showing effective CNT wetting. Additionally, the Raman G-band is located at approximately the same Raman shift across all cell/pin PNC and A-CNT array samples ($\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1} \pm 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on average), showing that the G-band is less affected by polymer infusion and curing. Collectively, these results provide process-structure insight into the PNC structural evolution as a function of polymer infusion into capillary densified A-CNT arrays.

3.3 X-ray Diffraction Analysis

Complementary to Raman spectroscopy, XRD analysis was employed to further investigate how the structure of high-density, patterned A-CNT-reinforced epoxy nanocomposites evolves with CNT V_f , polymer infiltration, and local confinement effects in the high V_f CNT cells and pins. The representative diffraction patterns in Figure 5 show the characteristic (100) and (110) carbon peaks at $2\theta \approx 43^\circ$ and 78° , respectively [14,31] for the as-grown A-CNT array, bulk 1% V_f PNC, and CNT cell and pin PNC samples. These arise from the (100) and (110) carbon planes and have a greater contribution to the diffraction pattern at higher CNT V_f , akin to the Raman spectroscopy results. The characteristic asymmetry in the (100) and (110) peaks for the MWCNT diffraction pattern in Figure 5 is due to the changes in the local curvature of the nanotube, which arise from particle size broadening (*i.e.*, slight variations in CNT diameter along its length) and strain broadening (*i.e.*, a distribution of graphitic crystallite d-spacing along the CNT length) [26,27,29]. Additionally, because of the vertical alignment of the A-CNTs in both the as-grown array and the PNCs, which also corresponds to their orthogonal orientation to the XRD stage, the typical (002) carbon peak arising from the inter-layer spacing of the MWCNT walls is not observed, since this d-spacing is not probed by the Bragg Brentano XRD geometry. The absence of the (002) peak in all tested samples confirms that the CNTs maintain their vertical alignment after densification, polymer infiltration, and PNC curing, demonstrating the viability of this process to create oriented and high density CNT composites. These results corroborate the CNT alignment observed in the SEM images described earlier, and they are also consistent with prior work reporting near-zero (002) peak intensity for highly aligned CNTs characterized in this XRD geometry [26-28].

Notable changes in the XRD peak positions and intensities are observed in Figure 5 as the CNT V_f in the polymer increases from the neat RTM6 epoxy ($V_f = 0\%$) to bulk PNC ($V_f \sim 1\%$), pin PNC ($V_f \sim 5\%$), cell PNC ($V_f \sim 8\%$) and pure A-CNT array samples, which have no polymer contribution. In addition to the aforementioned carbon peaks, the diffraction patterns also exhibit the broad epoxy peak at $2\theta \approx 21^\circ$ and a shoulder-type peak at $2\theta \approx 13^\circ$ [25,32,33] for the bulk PNC and cell/pin PNC samples, signifying the packing and crosslinking of polymer chains [31-33]. Since thermoset polymers, such as the RTM6 epoxy studied here, exhibit a cross-linked network structure after curing, they often show a broad, amorphous XRD peak below 25° owing to their small degree of crystallinity [2], as the matrix takes on a largely amorphous structure during the curing reaction [25,32]. All aforementioned XRD peaks in Figure 5 are interpreted to be a superposition of the CNT and RTM6 features. A new peak could signify the formation of a chemically distinct polymer interphase region directly surrounding the CNTs, as this has previously been determined to form approximately 10–100 nm in the vicinity of CNTs for a variety of polymers [11,30]. While it is plausible that an interphase could form for the cell and pin PNCs based on the inter-CNT spacing achieved here after capillary densification ($< 50 \text{ nm}$) [6,7,16], no additional XRD peaks besides the aforementioned carbon and epoxy peaks appear in Figure 5 when the A-CNTs are added to the polymer matrix.

Therefore, while the epoxy does not form a measurably distinct interphase for these PNC (consistent with past work on ~20% V_f bulk CNT-epoxy PNCs [11]) relatively small changes in the feature sizes related to polymer packing in the PNCs can still be observed to show the minor effect of CNT confinement on polymer behavior in these materials. For all samples listed above and in Figure 5

(in order of increasing CNT V_f), the $\sim 21^\circ$ peak is observed to monotonically shift down in position from $\sim 21.5^\circ$ to 21.0° , and the $\sim 13^\circ$ shoulder peak monotonically shifts down from $\sim 13.9^\circ$ to 13.6° as the CNT V_f in the epoxy matrix increases from 0 to $\sim 8\%$. This effect suggests that neat polymer packing in the matrix may be slightly reduced (*i.e.*, exhibiting a larger characteristic size) due to reduced inter-CNT spacing. Finally, no significant changes in the positions of the (100) peak for all samples in Figure 5 ($\sim 42.5^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ on average) or of the (110) peak ($\sim 77.8^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ on average) indicates that the CNTs do not significantly influence the crystallite packing or curvature in these directions, as the CNTs at higher V_f simply contribute more intensity to the diffraction pattern owing to the superposition of CNT and epoxy features.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the fabrication and structural characterization of multiwalled A-CNT-epoxy PNCs with novel mm-tall capillary-densified CNT cell and pin reinforcement were presented to investigate the process-structure relationships of these materials as a function of A-CNT V_f in the polymer matrix. These PNCs were created first via 1% V_f A-CNT chemical vapor deposition growth on Si substrates (a subset of which were mechanically hand-scribed for patterned CNT pin formation). Then, the patterned and bulk-scale A-CNT arrays were subjected to post-growth thermal annealing, capillary densification up to $\sim 8\%$ CNT V_f , and polymer infusion and curing with an aerospace-grade epoxy (RTM6) to create arrays of mm-tall CNT cell and pin PNCs for the first time. SEM, Raman spectroscopy, and XRD characterization were used to determine how CNT confinement influences polymer infiltration, wetting, atomic-scale structure, and the CNT-matrix morphology. In sum, this analysis shows that CNT alignment is maintained during all processing steps, complete wetting of the CNTs is achieved by the epoxy during infiltration, lower defect densities are observed for higher V_f PNCs, and fracture behavior is dominated by CNT-matrix pull-out due to the governing CNT-polymer matrix interactions. In the future, higher CNT V_f studies and additional property studies will be useful to further quantify the governing process-structure-property relations and CNT-polymer confinement effects for greater packing densities and other polymer systems, such as thermoplastics, where polymer interphase formation is more likely to occur and scale performance. Once these relations are known, the integration of capillary-densified CNTs may be realized for a wide range of composite applications, such as aerospace composites laminates and other nano-engineered hybrid structures.

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